

LUNAR IMPACT'S SEISMIC AND TELESCOPES EUROPEAN NETWORK FOR FLASH (LISTEN-FLASH): INTEGRATING AN INTERNATIONAL EARTH TELESCOPES NETWORK AND LUNAR SEISMIC NETWORK FOR MULTI-MESSENGER IMPACT SCIENCE AND SEISMOLOGY.

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Introduction: Terrestrial Planetary seismology aims to discover the interior of planets and their seismicity, allowing for unique comparison between the Earth and other terrestrial bodies. This is key for deciphering the fundamental processes of terrestrial-planet formation and evolution and remains the only way to determine the internal structure of terrestrial bodies, as demonstrated for the Moon⁰ or Mars^{0,0} by the thickness and stratification of the lunar^{0,0} or martian^{0,0} crusts and size and state of the lunar^{0,0} and martian^{0,0} cores.

After the Mars interior exploration by InSight seismometer, the next steps will be on the Moon, with four seismometer deployments planned before 2030 : the Chinese Chang'E-7 Lunar Seismometer, the NASA's Far Side Seismic Suite (FSS) with a French spare VBBZ InSight sensor and both NASA's Artemis-3 Lunar Environment Monitoring Station and Artemis 4 South Pole Seismic Station, the later again with the VBBZ sensor. Although having a high probability to operate sometime together, it is likely however that these stations might operate a significant time alone or with only another one. As for the stand-alone Mars InSight seismometer, a lunar single seismometer or even a pair of stations will not be able to locate quakes and inverse seismic structure. This is due to trade-off between the epicentral distance and the interior seismic velocities and therefore leads to significant errors in seismic velocities models. Impacts with known location and time are therefore game changers for internal structure inversions: first examples are the lunar artificial impacts (Saturn-VIB stages or Lunar ascent vehicles)^[11] with known locations and impact times which therefore provided precise lunar crustal structure^{[12],0}.

Impact seismology on the Moon: As demonstrated by the Apollo seismic experiment, impacts are the second source of seismic events after Deep Moon Quakes (DMQ), with 1743 impacts detected by the 4 LP seismometers over the 7.7 years of operation^[13], including at very large distance (Fig.1) plus 175 additional detections only on SP seismometers^[14]. With impacts detected at several stations, this makes an average of 100 impacts per year de-

tected by one Apollo LP seismometer^[15] with epicentral distances up to 3000 km (about 100° angular distance on the Moon), and about 100/year detected by Apollo SP^[16], corresponding to smaller but close events (< 50 km) for most of them.

Figure 1: Apollo records of a very large natural impact (star) (on 11/14/1976), 2000-3500 km from stations (triangle). Mass is 25–35 tons for 20 km/s impact velocity with source cut-off below 1 Hz⁰. FSS's vertical very broad band (VBBZ) sensor will record SNR > 1500 in the 0.5-2 Hz bandwidth (rms noise of 2×10^{-11} m/s).

Listen flash: Visible-light video cameras mounted on ground-based telescopes can monitor Lunar Impacts Flashes (LIF)^{[17],[18],[19]} occurring on the lunar Earth-shine side (non-sunlit) at night during impact event. The LISTEN-FLASH project^[20], selected by ERC as an advanced grant for 2025-2030, hinges on detecting and locating lunar impacts, essential for constraining interior models, akin to seismic studies on Mars. It does this by deploying a network of three Earth-based telescopes to monitor Lunar Impact Flashes in Infra-red day and night^[22]

on the Lunar near side south hemisphere, complementing data from FSS and other lunar seismometers [Fig 2]. As a result, FSS will seismically detect only about 23 impacts/year occurring on the near side. All these impacts will be large, but only 1/4 will occur when visible-light LIFs conditions are achieved, during Earth night and on non-sunlit south hemisphere. This synergy enables precise impact location and timing, crucial for mapping lunar crustal and mantle structures of the lunar south hemisphere, including Schrödinger impact basin and South Pole shallow layers.

Figure 2: Expected detection threshold for FSS (in cyan) and for LEMS (in yellow), assuming 10x worth sensibility for LEMS for a rate of 14 events per year, distance dependence of 0 and SNR of 5/50 for P and S. Note that the event of Fig 6, at 985 km (first red line) with SNR > 100 for S, fits well to expectations. Green rectangles are the 2 FOV of LIFs cameras and the second red line is the 90° epicentral limit.

The first telescopes, built by OCA, is already in operation at CALERN and is now upgraded toward full automatization. It provided already its first LIF observation^[23]. The two next telescopes are now in construction and will be deployed in the coming year. Thanks to international collaboration, the LISTEN-FLASH network will be completed with observing sites in Hawaii and in Japan, and additional collaboration is planned with observations in visible light.

Moreover, the project pioneers a multi-messenger approach in planetary science by combining seismic waveforms from impacts, high-resolution imaging of impact craters and impact digital twins to understand impact dynamics, lunar scattering and attenuation and lunar subsurface properties comprehensively. It aims to establish empirical relations between impact characteristics, seismic source parameters and seismic signals, enhancing our understanding of impact processes and enabling “natural” controlled seismology using impacts for future planetary exploration. With a robust implementation plan aligned with lunar mission timelines, LISTEN FLASH promises to deliver ground breaking insights into planetary seismology. It leverages expertise from planetary seismology, impact observations, and instrumentation, supported by international collaborations, to address funda-

mental questions about planetary interiors and enhance our understanding of planetary formation and impacts processes.

References: [1] Lognonné et al. (2003) , Earth Plan. Sci. Let., 6637, 1-18, [2] Khan et al. (2021), Science, 373, 434-438, [3] Drilleau, et al. (2023). Geophys. Res. Lett. 50, e2023GL104601. [4] Chen et al. (2006), Earth Planet Sci. Let., 243, 1-14, [5] Lognonné et al. (2020), Nature geoscience, 13, 213-220 [6] Knapmeyer-Endrun et al. (2021) Science, 373, 438-443 [7] Weber et al. (2011), Science, 331, 309-312 [8] Garcia et al. (2011), Phys. Earth. Planet. Int., 188, 96-113, [9] Stähler et al. (2021), Science, 373, 443-448 [10] Samuel et al. (2023), Nature, 622, 712-717, [11] Latham et al. (1970), Science, 170, 620-626, [12] Toksöz et al. (1974), Rev. Geophys., 12, 539-567 [13] Nakamura, et al. (1981). UTIG Technical Report, No. 118. University of Texas Institute for Geophysics. [14] Onodera, K. (2024). New views of lunar seismicity brought by analysis of newly discovered moonquakes in Apollo short-period seismic data. J. Geophys. Res: Planets, 129, e2023JE008153. [15] Gudkova et al. (2015) Earth and Planetary Science Letters, 427, 57-65 [16] Lognonne et al. (2009), J. Geophys. Res., 114, E12003 [17] Ortiz et al. (1999) Astron Astrophys, 343, L57-L60 [18] Ortiz et al. (2000), Nature, 405, 921-923 [19] Bouley et al. (2012), Icarus, 218, 115-124 [20] <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101199624> [21] Sheward et al. (2024), Monthly Notice of the Royal Astr. Soc., 529, 3828-3837 [22] Sheward et al. (2026) abstract 12566, EGU 2026 conference.